

MODEL UNCERTAINTIES ON STRENGTHENED RC WALLS

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ABSTRACT

Numerical methods of structural analysis enable consideration of material and geometrical non-linearity of CFRP-strengthened reinforced concrete structures. The effect of variability of materials and geometry can be relatively well described, while the model uncertainty is not yet well understood. The present contribution focus on resistance model uncertainties in the analysis of reinforced concrete walls strengthened with CFRP. Available definitions of the model uncertainties are reviewed and statistical characteristics of the model uncertainties are obtained from previous studies.

KEYWORDS

Model uncertainties; Numerical analysis; Reliability; Structural walls; CFRP; Reinforced concrete,

INTRODUCTION

In the last decades, nonlinear finite element analysis (NLFEA) has shown potential for investigating the behavior of reinforced concrete (RC) structures. A nonlinear analysis can capture the concrete cracking and steel reinforcement yielding, allowing a more realistic estimation of the structure's load-carrying capacity and internal forces redistribution. Despite these advantages, to date, the use of NFLEAs in the field of RC structural engineering for design purposes is scarce. Indeed, most applications of NLFEA are limited to research purposes, e.g., the modeling of executed experimental tests of RC specimens. Different reasons justified this fact, such as large computation time, diversity of theoretical approaches, uncertainties in the modeling of reinforced concrete behavior, and the expertise required for the engineer to perform the analysis and interpret the results.

The model and material uncertainties in the context of structural design can be mitigated through the use of safety formats. In the case of design codes, the partial safety factor method is a widely accepted alternative. In contrast, applying safety format methods for nonlinear analysis is still under discussion. This paper aims to investigate the model uncertainties of CFRP-strengthened RC structural walls, which are related to the inherent simplifications adopted in the constitutive models and the finite element approximation. For this purpose, numerical analyses of wall experiments reported in the literature were simulated to determine the model uncertainty factor using the methodology proposed by Červenka et al. (2018).

MODEL UNCERTAINTY

According to the Probabilistic Model Code of the Joint Committee on Structural Safety -JCSS (2012), the model uncertainty describes simplifications in the mathematical description of real behavior. It is meant to cover imprecision and incompleteness of the relevant theoretical models for resistance and can be formulated as Equation 1.

$$\theta = \frac{R_{exp}}{R_{sim}} \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

Where θ is the model uncertainty, R_{exp} is the resistance found by experiment and R_{sim} is the resistance obtained by the model simulating the real structure.

Considering θ as a random variable, it can be evaluated for a series of tests and its statistical parameters can be determined. For this purpose, a log-normal statistical distribution can be adopted and described by parameters such as mean μ_θ and coefficient of variation V_θ . Moreover, a partial factor of model uncertainty can be calculated based on this probabilistic model.

$$\gamma_{Rd} = \frac{\exp(\alpha_R \beta \times V_\theta)}{\mu_\theta} \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

A safety measure is described by the reliability index $\beta = 3.8$. The sensitivity factor $\alpha_R = 0.4 \times 0.8 = 0.32$, where 0.8 is a sensitivity factor for resistance and 0.4 for model uncertainty as a non-dominant entity. Both the reliability index and sensitivity factor follow values recommended by the *fib* Model Code 2010.

CASE STUDY

The present investigation is based on the test of 18 bearing RC walls, which include 5 reference non-strengthened walls and 13 Externally Bonded Carbon Fiber Polymer (EB-CFRP) strengthened walls subjected to one-way action. These tests were gathered from the experimental works of Mohammed et al. (2013) and Lima et al. (2019). All specimens, supported solely at the top and bottom, were subjected to the interaction between unidirectional bending and axial force induced by an initial load eccentricity ($tw/6$) (see Figure 1). The dimensions are listed in Table 1, which includes walls and opening sizes. The simulations were performed with prior knowledge of the experimental test results. In all cases, material parameters for simulations were provided from the tests on material samples accompanying the experiments. In the case of concrete, only the mean compressive strength was typically investigated. When necessary, a conversion factor (0.8) was used to relate the compressive strengths of cylindrical and cubic samples. Other parameters, such as Young's modulus (E_c), tensile strength (f_t) and fracture energy (G_f), were derived using the relation given in *fib* Model Code 2010 and are presented in Table 2. The plastic displacement, which is an important parameter for simulating concrete softening behavior, was adopted as 0.1mm based on previous authors' experience. Parameters for reinforcement included yield stress and Young's modulus. For brevity, only selected results are shown here in this study. All simulations were performed in the ATENA software.

Figure 1: Experimental condition and geometry (in mm) of tested RC walls.

Table 1: RC walls geometry.

Reference	Wall	% of wall opening	Wall size (mm)			Opening size (mm)	
			H	L	t_w	H_o	L_o
Mohammed et al. (2013)	OW1a,b,c	5	800	400	40	170	95
	OW2a,b,c	10				240	135
	OW3a,b,c	20				340	185
	OW4a,b,c	30				420	230
Lima et al. (2019)	OW-NF,AF,DF,CF,WF,PF	15	1200	1200	40	450	450

Table 2: Parameters for constitutive model of RC walls (CC3DNonLinCementitious2).

Reference	Wall	Known parameters			Derived parameters		
		f_c (MPa)	E_s (GPa)	f_y (MPa)	E_c (GPa)	f_t (MPa)	G_f (N/m)
Mohammed et al. (2013)	OW1a	15.99	205	478	25141	1.20	120
	OW2a	13.94			24017	0.98	117
	OW3a	15.57			24919	1.16	120
	OW4a	15.79			25131	1.20	120
	OW1b	14.97			24595	1.09	119
	OW2b	17.08			25700	1.31	122
	OW3b	18.24			26269	1.41	123
	OW4b	15.06			24644	1.10	119
	OW1c	14.72			24457	1.07	119
	OW2c	15.64			24957	1.16	120
	OW3c	16.36			25334	1.24	121
	OW4c	17.04			25680	1.30	122
Lima et al. (2019)	WO-NF	54.7	200	500	37882	3.96	150
	WO-AF	54.7			37882	3.96	150
	WO-DF	55.0			37951	3.97	150
	WO-CF	62.6			39624	4.20	154
	WO-WF	62.6			39624	4.20	154
	WO-PF	64.9			40104	4.27	155

One-way RC walls by Mohammed et al. (2013)

The experimental program tested a total of sixteen 1/3 scale RC walls with openings comprising four identical series of four specimens (see Figure 1a). Series 1 and 2, designated as WO1–WO4 and WO1a–WO4a, respectively, were tested without CFRP. While series 3 and 4 designated as WO1b–WO4b and WO1c–WO4c, respectively, were tested with EB-CFRP strengthening the vicinity of the openings. The authors evaluated the influence of different opening sizes and strengthening patterns on the wall's resistance. One reinforcement layer was placed centrally within the wall cross-section providing the minimum requirement of the ACI 318 (2002). The variable opening sizes comprised 5%, 10%, 20%, and 30% of the walls' area. The strengthening methods were based on the externally bonded CFRP (EB-CFRP) technique, where two patterns of CFRP were applied on both the tension and compression faces along the opening (AF) and diagonally on the corners (DF), as illustrated in Figure 2. In order to analyze walls with similar geometrical aspects, the present study will focus on series 2 (WO1a-WO4a), 3 (WO1b-WO4b) and 4 (WO1c-WO4c). For these walls, dimensions are detailed in Table 1, from where can be calculated aspect ratio (H/L), slenderness ratio (H/t_w), and thickness ratio (L/t_w) of 2, 20 and 10, respectively. Reinforcing and material parameters are given in Table 2.

Figure 2: Strengthening patterns used in the tested RC walls.

The numerical model of concrete consists of hexahedral solid (brick) elements with 20-node and a quadratic displacement approximation function. The mesh size was uniform in the whole RC wall. A mesh sensitivity study was carried out on distinctive mesh seeds comprising length:width:thickness proportions of $2 \times 2 \times 1 \text{ cm}^3$ (fine), $3 \times 3 \times 1 \text{ cm}^3$ (medium), and $4 \times 4 \times 1 \text{ cm}^3$ (coarse). The results are presented in Figure 3, confirming that the medium mesh with 4 elements through the wall thickness is sufficiently representative. The mesh choice took into account the time expense, good quality of the cracks representation, and that proportions higher than 3:1 can have degenerated displacement fields.

Figure 3: Mesh analysis of RC wall.

To model the CFRP material, quadrilateral elements with 8-node and quadratic displacement approximation functions were used considering the plane stress state. The corresponding mesh size was $1 \times 1 \text{ cm}^2$. Simulations considered a perfect rigid interface model as no slipping between strengthening material and concrete was noticed on the experimental tests. Material parameters for the CFRP constitutive model are presented in Table 3. In Figure 4, it is compared the crack patterns at failure of strengthened models and experimental tests. Simulation shows the colored iso-areas indicating the crack opening. It can be observed that the models provide a reasonable estimate of the crack development. In series 2, experimental tests reported that failure occurred in the tension face due to CFRP rupture or splitting from the concrete. However, observed failure in the simulations was governed mostly by concrete crushing at the compression wall face, without rupture of the strengthening material. Upon examination of Figure 5 showing CFRP stresses in the tension face at rupture, the stresses are inferior to the material resistance (4300MPa) and the limit for CFRP-governed failure established by ACI 440.2R (2017). From series 3 experimental tests, it was reported

rupture similar to non-strengthened cases, governed by concrete crushing. This failure mode was confirmed by the simulations where it can be noted the DF-pattern low stresses and crack opening (see Figures 4 and 5). Thus, the strengthening should have a small influence in this scenario. The concrete crushing on the compression face of the models is shown in Figure 6, which was also observed on the experimental test. In the simulation, crushing is assumed by initiating the concrete softening regime under compression associated with the equivalent plastic strain. Two horizontal bands lateral to the opening entered the concrete softening regime at the moment of failure.

Figure 4: Comparison of failure horizontal cracks on strengthened models.

Figure 5: CFRP stresses on the tension face.

Table 3: Parameters for constitutive model of CFRP.

Reference	Known parameters (CFRP)			Derived parameters (epoxy)	
	f_f (MPa)	E_f (MPa)	t_f (mm)	E_{ep} (MPa)	t_{ep} (mm)
Mohammed et al. (2013)	4800	230000	0.167	100	1.0
Lima et al. (2019)	4300	234000	0.128	100	1.0

Figure 6: Concrete crushing on the wall compression face.

One-way RC walls by Lima et al. (2019)

Six RC walls from the experimental program are considered, including one reference non-strengthened wall (see Figure 1b). All specimens were lightly reinforced with a central mesh of orthogonal steel bars to meet the minimum requirements of AS 3600 (2018). The authors evaluated the influence of different strengthening patterns on the wall’s resistance. A central opening size remained constant, comprising 14% of the wall’s area. The vicinity of the openings were CFRP-strengthened on the tension face with the configurations illustrated in Figure 2. Only for WF-pattern, the horizontal and vertical CFRP was wrapped from tension to compression face. For these walls, dimensions are detailed in Table 1, from where can be calculated aspect ratio (H/L), slenderness ratio (H/tw), and thickness ratio (L/tw) of 1, 30 and 30, respectively. Steel reinforcement and concrete materials are given in Table 2, where the additional parameters needed for the numerical simulations can be found.

The simulation strategy adopted was similar to the previous case, which consists of hexahedral solid (brick) elements with 20-node and quadratic displacement approximation function, uniform medium mesh size ($3 \times 3 \times 1 \text{ cm}^3$) in the whole RC wall, and a perfect rigid interface between concrete and CFRP. As a consequence of the geometry of CFRP disposal, in the CF and WF patterns were necessary to combine triangular and quadrilateral mesh. Material parameters for CFRP are given in Table 3. Figure 7 presents a comparison between experimental and numerical cracking, where reasonable accuracy in predicting the crack opening can be noted. Bending failure was predominant in these walls. Lima et al. (2019) report that there was adequate evidence to confirm that some compressive crushing failure also occurred on the experimental test. In the simulation, however, no concrete crushing was observed as the equivalent plastic strain remained below softening regime. Failure of the WO-CF model is illustrated in Figure 8. Upon examination of this figure, it is noticed the appearance of a horizontal main crack in the center of the model causing all vertical reinforcement to switch from compression to tension. The vertical CFRP along the opening also collaborates with resistance; its stress (286 MPa) is inferior to the maximum strength and the ACI 440.2R (2017) limit for CFRP-governing failure.

Figure 7: Comparison of failure horizontal cracks on strengthened models.

Figure 8: Failure of strengthened models.

Figure 9 presents the relationship between experimental and numerical results. A safety trend is perceived when the reference tests are from Mohammed et al. (2013) and an unsafe trend when they are from Lima et al. (2019). To assess the model uncertainty, Equation 1 was employed in separated

groups and to all specimens, where the distribution parameters mean and coefficient of variation were calculated. The results are summarized in Table 4 and Table 5, comprising non-strengthened and EB-CFRP strengthened cases, respectively, for each group of tests and the whole set. The model uncertainty safety factors (Equation 2) were also calculated and presented in Table 6. As the model uncertainty was clearly different between the two reference campaign tests, it was decided to compute the model uncertainties separately.

Figure 9: Overall comparison of load results.

The safety factor depends on the mean model uncertainty, representing the average model fit, and the coefficient of variation, which reflects the random variability of model imperfections (Červenka et al., 2018). In the case of simulations of Mohammed et al. (2013) tests, the mean model uncertainty is greater than 1, indicating that, on average, the model underestimates the tests. This is reflected in the smaller safety factor $\gamma_{Rd} = 0.85$ (non-strengthened) and $\gamma_{Rd} = 0.785$ (CFRP-strengthened). It is worth mention these tests were performed in reduced scale specimens cast with normal strength concrete; thus, it is possible that size effect has influenced the results. Furthermore, it is reasonable to assume the load eccentricity is difficult to maintain along the test, as it deals with very small values, which could explain why the DF-pattern was more effective in resistance than the AF-pattern, observed in the experimental tests.

Table 4: Model uncertainties for non-strengthened walls.

Reference	Model	R_{exp} (kN)	R_{sim} (kN)	θ	Group
Mohammed et al. (2013)	OW1a	100.0	89.6	1.12	$\mu_{\theta} = 1.417$ $V_{\theta} = 0.153$
	OW2a	95.3	65.8	1.45	
	OW3a	85.0	57.8	1.47	
	OW4a	73.7	45.1	1.63	
Lima et al. (2019)	WO-NF	266	366.7	0.73	-
All specimens				$\mu_{\theta} = 1.279$ $V_{\theta} = 0.283$	

In the case of Lima et al. (2019) reference tests, the mean model uncertainty is approximately 1, indicating that, on average, the models equal the tests. However, the coefficient of variation (21.9%) indicates large dispersion in relation to the average value of the frequency distribution. This is reflected in the higher safety factor $\gamma_{Rd} = 1.302$ (CFRP-strengthened), compensating for the random variability.

A safety factor greater than one can be selected in order to remain on the safe side, which leads to $\gamma_{Rd} = 1.395$ when designing EB-CFRP strengthened OW walls.

Table 5: Model uncertainties for CFRP-strengthened walls.

Reference	R_{exp} (kN)	R_{sim} (kN)	θ	Group
Mohammed et al. (2013)				
OW1b	149.9	102.0	1.46	$\mu_{\theta} = 1.66$ $V_{\theta} = 0.219$
OW2b	139.1	99.0	1.41	
OW3b	108.0	87.1	1.24	
OW4b	82.0	63.1	1.30	
OW1c	175.4	85.5	2.05	
OW2c	157.2	77.8	2.02	
OW3c	138.5	64.7	2.14	
OW4c	84.8	50.5	1.68	
Lima et al. (2019)				
WO-AF	336	373.7	0.90	$\mu_{\theta} = 1.00$ $V_{\theta} = 0.219$
WO-DF	309	372.0	0.83	
WO-CF	559	407.7	1.37	
WO-WF	415	402.7	1.03	
WO-PF	360	409.3	0.88	
All specimens			$\mu_{\theta} = 1.41$ $V_{\theta} = 0.321$	

Table 6: Safety factor for model uncertainties.

Reference	Type of wall	μ_{θ}	V_{θ}	γ_{Rd}
Mohammed et al. (2013)	Non-strengthened	1.417	0.153	0.850
	CFRP-strengthened	1.663	0.219	0.785
Lima et al. (2019)	CFRP-strengthened	1.002	0.219	1.302
All specimens		1.373	0.308	1.395

CONCLUSION

The safety factor for model uncertainty of EB-CFRP strengthened walls was evaluated. Simulations were based on 18 bearing walls with a central opening subjected to an in-plane eccentric load. In these walls, different opening sizes and strengthening patterns were used in the specimens. The model uncertainty significantly varied when calculated from different reference experimental tests. The simulations used the fracture-plastic material model implemented in ATENA software. The assessment of model uncertainty was based on a probabilistic concept of model imperfections. Assuming a log-normal statistical distribution, sensitive factor $\alpha_R = 0.32$ and the reliability index $\beta = 3.8$, the overall global safety factor of model uncertainty was derived from CFRP-strengthened OW walls as $\gamma_{Rd} = 1.395$, however, it encompasses two groups of experiments with different specimens sizes and concrete strength. Due to the scarce number of experimental investigations on EB-CFRP RC walls, it seems reasonable to differentiate $\gamma_{Rd} = 1.302$ based on Mohammed experimental tests (with varying opening sizes) and $\gamma_{Rd} = 0.785$ based on Lima experimental tests. Log-normal distribution is often assumed as a suitable probabilistic description of the model uncertainty, however, the authors recognize that more experimental data is necessary to better support this assumption.

The safety factor derived in this study is limited to the numerical solutions based on the fracture-plastic constitutive model and software ATENA.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.

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